

THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE EDUCATION OF LISTENING STRATEGIES IN UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: Nowadays learning foreign languages is becoming increasingly popular in Uzbekistan. This is the result of the actions of our President Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev. The first step that he did in 2017 with his 5-step strategies for the development of Uzbekistan has given significant results. Then he issued a decree about the development of the education system, specifically teaching foreign languages.

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The short information about 5-step strategies for the development of Uzbekistan.

1. Priority areas of improvement of the state and community construction system. Strengthening the role of the legislative chamber and political parties in deepening democratic reforms and modernization of the country: to increase the role of the legislative chamber in the system of state power, to further expand its powers to solve important tasks related to the country's internal and foreign policy and to exercise parliamentary control over the activities of the executive power.

2. Priorities for ensuring the rule of law and further reforming the judicial system. Ensuring the true independence of the judiciary, increasing the authority of the court, democratizing and improving the judicial system: to increase the status of judges and court staff, the level of material incentives and social security, to strengthen the material and technical base of courts

3. The priority direction of economic development and liberalization. Further strengthening of macroeconomic stability and maintaining high economic growth rates: maintaining macroeconomic balance, ensuring high growth rates of gross domestic product due to the deepening of structural and institutional changes based on the adopted medium-term programs maintaining the balance of the State budget at all levels while maintaining the social orientation of expenses, improving inter-budgetary relations aimed at strengthening the revenue part of local budgets.

4. Priority areas of social sector development. Consistent increase in population employment and real income. Increase the real monetary income and purchasing power of the population, further reducing the number of low-income families and the level of differentiation of the population's income.

5. Priorities in the field of security, international harmony, and religious tolerance and a thoughtful, mutually beneficial, and practical foreign policy. Priority directions in the field of ensuring security, religious tolerance, and inter-ethnic harmony. Protection of the constitutional system, sovereignty, and territorial integrity of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Ensuring information security and improving the information protection system, organizing timely and appropriate actions against threats in the information field.

From that time teachers started to work on their teaching methodology, mostly modern technologies especially computers and phones to prepare proficient workers. Shavkat Mirziyoyev let to open private schools, kinder gardens and a number of private schools specialized in teaching several languages and IT technologies. The next step was done in 2021 from the news that to be accepted to the MBA program students must know English at list to B2 level. This kind of lowest increased the number of students who want to learn English. Moreover, students want to do it faster than it was several years ago. The teachers who want to earn more money are tried to guarantee exact results for several months. They are trying to use the newest methodology of teaching. They do it by watching teaching methodologies of

teachers from other countries or by observing other teachers who have more students.

Now we can see great improvements in teaching English. The approach of modern teachers has changed. Now they are focusing on the development of general skills rather than specific aspects like band 9 tips for listening, reading, writing, and speaking. As I am working as a teacher I know the methods and books that are being used to improve the skills of the students. Firstly, they are doing passive listening that suits their level. Then week by week they will upper the level of the recordings. They will keep doing so till the exams. A month before they will start doing real practice from Cambridge books in a week. Then students will know which result they can expect from exams. There are seven incredible steps I learned to improve the listening abilities of students.

Step One: Pre-Listening

1. Set a goal.

Guidelines for teaching listening to students. According to Funk and Funk (1989), it's important to have a goal or purpose for every listening activity. First, begin by stating a purpose. This will guide students to know where to focus, enabling them to achieve success.

2. Build Background.

Next, help students connect what they already know with what they will hear in the audio story by asking questions about their personal experiences with the topic. Explain what students need to understand before listening, and preview vocabulary words. Invite them to think about relevant prior knowledge, anticipate the subject of the story, or otherwise engage actively in preparing for the story.

3. Prepare the Environment.

If playing the story out loud to the whole class, limit distraction by making the environment at home or in school as quiet as possible. For instance, use headphones for listening if appropriate.

4. Introduce Listening Strategies

Next, introduce tools and strategies for successful listening (see below).

Step Two: Teaching During Listening

5. Scaffold Note-Taking.

Students can use a listening organizer to help them focus on important ideas and details while listening to the story, which can help to deepen their understanding. For example, listening organizers might include T-charts, Venn diagrams, or a blank page to keep track of a character's actions in the story. Such organizers can guide students in taking notes to help them focus their listening and teach them strategies to support comprehension in other contexts.

6. Explain Problem-Solving Strategies.

If students do not understand a word or idea, they can use clues from the story to make a guess. If they listen independently, they can stop the audio and think or listen as needed. They can be “problem-solving listeners”. These strategies should be taught before students begin listening with reminders provided as needed.

Step Three: Post-Listening

7. Reflect on the Audio Story.

Finally, engage students in synthesizing what they learned from listening to the story with a focus on key understanding goals. For example, ask students to respond to listening comprehension questions in writing and then share their responses. This could be either with a partner, a small group, or in front of the whole class. Discuss key themes in the story and encourage students to make connections to other texts or experiences. Students can respond to questions about the story through writing, speaking in conversation, recording themselves speaking, or a combination.

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